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MUNDARIJA

QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI YASHIL ENERGIYA: BARCHA UCHUN MUHIM MASALA.....	13
Muxiddin Kalonov	
MOLIYAVIY INNOVATSIYALAR: IQTISODIY MOHIYATI, QO‘LLANILISHI VA RIVOJLANISHI.....	19
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
SAVDO KORXONALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA STATISTIK TAHLIL USULLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING AHAMIYATI.....	24
Sabirova Oysuluv Shonazarovna	
KORXONANING MEBEL MAXSULOTLARI BOZORIDAGI O‘RNINI KENGAYTIRISH USULLARI	30
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA KO‘RSATKICHLARI TIZIMINING FUNKSIONAL JIHATI.....	35
Alabayev Sobitxon	
MAMLAKATIMIZDA MAHSULOTLARNING MUVOFIQLIGINI BAHOLASH AMALIYOTI.....	40
Zakirov Ansabxon Akaidinovich	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	48
Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна	
KORXONALAR FAOLIYATIDA DEBITOR VA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNI BOSHQARISH	55
Mirzayev Ozod Furkatovich	
AHOLI PUL DAROMADLARI VA HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH KO‘RSATKICHLARI O‘RTASIDAGI EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL.....	59
Qodirov Farrux Ergash o‘g‘li	
BUDJET RESURSLARI SHAKLLANISHIDA HUDUDNING SOLIQ SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIK.....	64
Yuldashev Adhamjon Axadjonovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHI TUSHUNCHASIGA NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	69
Muydinov Xusniddin Nuriddin o‘g‘li	
МЕТОДИКА УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ ПОТОКАМИ В СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОГО УЧЕТА	73
Минутдинова Лилия Тагировна, Машарипов Озод Алимович	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	78
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
RAQAMLI TECHNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA SMART TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING DOLZARBLIGI	84
Sobirjonov Muxiddin Toxirjon o‘g‘li	
TO‘LOVGA QOBILIYATSIZLIK HOLATIDAGI KORXONALARDA TUGATISH BALANSINI TUZISH.....	90
Nabiyev Gofurjon Nosirjon o‘g‘li	
O‘ZBEKISTON SANOATINING “YASHIL” IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TAYOTGANLIGI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CHEKLOVLAR	96
Habibullayev Oybek Asliddin o‘g‘li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTSEPTSIYASINING EVOLYUTSIYASI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	102
Allayarov Suxrob Rustamovich	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA TO‘G‘RIDAN-TO‘G‘RI CHET EL INVESTITSIYALARINING MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI ROLI	107
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich, Boynazarova Matluba Xatamovna	

HUDUDIY IJTIMOY TENGLIK VA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI YUMSHATISHDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI OMILLARI.....	114
Durumov Temur G'olibovich	
TRANSPORT TARMOG'I VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOTNING ASOSIY TARMOQLARI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIKNI MODELASHTIRISH (SURXANDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	121
Turayev Baxtiyor Ergashevich, Aymatov Sirojiddin To'raqul o'g'li	
РОЛЬ ЭНЕРГЕТИКИ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РОСТА ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	134
Нигматуллаева Гулчехра Нуруллаевна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI VA UNDA SIFAT MENEJMENTINING ROLI.....	139
Yuldashev Iskandar Bahromovich	
YER QA'RIDAN FOYDALANUVCHILARGA SOLIQ SOLISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	145
Zoxidov Ismatjon Yunusjon o'g'li	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA TURIZM INDUSTRIYASIDA INNOVATSION BIZNES-MODELLAR.....	151
Shaxinabonu Choriyeva	
AVTOTRANSPORT – EKSPEDITSIYA XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA MARKETING KONTSEPSIYASI.....	157
Ergasheva Mukhabbat Abdusamatovna	
“YASHIL” ENERGIYA ISHLAB CHIQRUVCHI KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI SOLIQQA TORTISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	163
Toshtemirov To'liqin Toirjonovich	
DAVLAT IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SIYOSIY INSTITUTLARNING ROLI VA UNI KUCHAYTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	166
O. Nurmuradov	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQAMLI BANK TEXNOLOGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ASOSLARI	171
Meyliqulov Shaxboz Xolmamat o'g'li	
СВЯЗНОСТЬ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ.....	176
Ташматов Гайрат Ровшанович, Содиков Авазбек Мадаминович	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASI TURIZM SOHASINI RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	183
Zarikeyeva Miyasar Maratovna	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYASI.....	187
Saidrahmatova Zuhraxon Saidazim qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON KONCHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA INVESTITSION JARAYONLARNI BOSHQARISH VA INNOVATSION XAVFLARNI KAMAYTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	192
Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA QULAY INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI.....	196
Xuramov Zafar Rajabaliyevich	
PAHTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARIDA XOMASHYO TA'MINOTI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING XORIJ DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	201
Zakirov Abduazim Abdurashidovich	
НОВЫЙ ЭТАП ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ РЫНОЧНЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	206
Махкамов Ибраим	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENTSIYALARI.....	213
Xushmuradov Oman, Ismoilov Sherzod Ismoil o'g'li	
GLOBALIZATSIYA SHAROITIDA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT NAZARIYASI.....	217
Mo'ydinov Xurshidbek Abdullayevich	
DORIVOR O'SIMLIKLARNI QAYTA ISHLASHNING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	221
Usmonov Mirg'ulom Xoshim o'g'li	

BARQAROR IQTISODIY O‘SISHGA YERISHISHDA SUN’IY INTELLEKT TIZIMLARINI QO‘LLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH (XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI MISOLIDA)	227
Nasrulloev Hayotjon Xabibulloevich	
НЕЙРОИНТУИТИВНЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И ЕГО РОЛЬ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ РИСКАМИ В БИЗНЕСЕ.....	233
Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович	
RESURLARNI SOLIQQA TORTISH AMALIYOTINING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI VA ULARNING MILLIY SOLIQQA TIZIMIDA QO‘LLASH MASALALARI	240
Nasimdjanoov Yunusjon Zoxidovich	
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARI UCHUN QO‘LLANILAYOTGAN SOLIQQA TORTISH MEKANIZMLARI	246
Akbarov Akramjon Ibragimzhonovich	
TO‘QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARIDA “YASHIL” MARKETINGNI JORIY ETISHNING DOLZARB JIHATLARI	250
Bazarova Fayyoza Tuxtamurodovna	
INSON KAPITALI VA IQTISODIYOTNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYASI.....	255
Muzaffar Raximov	
UY-JOY KOMMUNAL XO‘JALIGINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI.....	259
Odamboyev Oybek Ravshanbek o‘g‘li	
INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS’ APPROACHES TO ATTRACTING INVESTMENT IN HUMAN CAPITAL	268
Akhmadaliyeva Nikholakhon	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR ORQALI KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	273
Vohobov Hikmatillo Ma‘mirjon o‘g‘li	
ФОРСАЙТ И ЭКОНОМИЧНЫЕ ИННОВАЦИИ КАК ДРАЙВЕРЫ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТОРГОВЛИ САМАРКАНДА	280
Tohirova Gullola Mirkamolovna	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI BOSHQARISHDA KASB-HUNAR TA‘LIMI BITIRUVCHILARINING O‘RNI	287
Toshpulatov Sherzod Xaydarkulovich	
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ECOTOURISM: INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES FOR ADVANCING GREEN TOURISM.....	292
Barno Erkayeva	
AGROTURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	296
Baymuradova Iroda Shermamatovna, Mardonova Zarifa Numonjonovna	
DAVLAT BUDJET NAZORATI TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	301
B.Sh.Mirzayev	
YOSHLAR BANDLIGIDA KO‘NIKMALAR NOMUTANOSIBLIGI MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI.....	307
Rahmatxo‘jayev Axrorxo‘ja Akmal o‘g‘li	
TO‘QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARINING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI TAHLIL QILISH VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARINI BAHOLASH.....	311
Oqboyev Alisher Rasuljanovich	
РЕИНЖИНИРИНГ БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССОВ И ИХ РОЛЬ В РАЗВИТИИ БАНКОВСКОГО БИЗНЕСА.....	317
Рахимходжаева Нодира Саидахраловна	
QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI TA‘MINOT ZANJIRI JARAYONLARINING HOZIRGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	323
Ermonov Farrux	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKILLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA MOLIYAVIY NAZORATNI INNOVATSION TA‘LIM YO‘NALISHLARINI YO‘LGA QO‘YISH ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI.....	329
Turg‘unov Bahtiyor Nuriddinovich	

MARKAZIY OSIYODA SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH VA HAMKORLIKNING DOLZARB MASALALARI	334
Amanbaev Amanali Orazbaevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI TURDAGI LOGISTIKA XIZMATLARINING USLUBIY ASOSLARI.....	338
Z. Teshayev	
O'ZBEKISTON AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSIYA XIZMATLARI SOHASINING AMALDAGI HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH.....	343
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVDA LEADERSHIP 4.0 TAMOYILLARINI JORIY ETISH SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	349
Ismailov Allayor Rashidovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI.....	355
Yusupov Farxod Adamboyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI O'RNI VA UNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNI USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	359
Abdullaeva Nilufar Javdat qizi	
MINTAQADA SANOAT KORXONALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING SOLISHTIRMA EKONOMETRIK MODELLARI (SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	363
Saatmurotov Shohrux Zafar o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORI: RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI VA ISTIQBOLLI IMKONIYATLAR	369
Abdurazaqov Jasur Abdunasimovich	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR YORDAMIDA NORASMIY VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI QISQARTIRISHNING QO'SHIMCHA IMKONIYATLARI TO'G'RSIDA.....	374
Nasrullayev Hikmatullo Habibulloyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MAQSADIDA "XIZMATLAR IPOTEKASI" MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARINI AMALIYOTGA JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	379
Uskenbayeva Dilnoza Boxodir qizi	
ЭКОНОМИКО-СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ ПРИ ВОЗДЕЛЫВАНИИ ЛУКА В ДЖИЗАКСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	384
Суюнов Шохзодбек Мурод угли	
XORIJY DAVLATLAR SANOAT IQTISODIYOTIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH TAJRIBASI (YAPONIYA, KOREYA VA GERMANIYA MISOLIDA)	389
Mansurova Sayyora Baxtiyor Kizi	
KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARAJATLARI HISOBGA OLIHDA XORIY TAJRIBASINI QO'LLASH	395
Raxmatov Baxriddin Baxtiyor o'g'li	
PECULIARITIES OF THE IRRIGATION WATER DELIVERY PAYMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	399
Muminov Sherzod Kholmiraevich	
DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS FOR EXPORT	404
Azimov R.B.	
AHOLI JON BOSHIGA UMUMIY DAROMADLAR HAJMINI TREND MODELLAR ASOSIDA PROGNOZLASH	409
Xolto'rayev Islom Ilhomovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA YANGI BANDLIK SHAKLLARI	416
Sayipov Begzod Rahimovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING YANGI DAVR SHAROITIDA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASH USULLARI VA INDIKATORLARI	422
Sadikov Iskandar Gayratovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI AKTIVLARINING SAMARADORLIGINI IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI	427
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi o'g'li	

MAHALLIY BUDJET SOLIQLI DAROMADLARI BAZASI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA SOLIQLAR TA'SIRCHANLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	433
<i>Isoqov Zafarjon Zokirjonovich</i>	
TOSHKENT SHAHRIDAGI YIRIK SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILARNING SOLIQ QARZDORLIGI TAHLILI	438
<i>Soipov Boburmirzo Nosirjon o'g'li</i>	
РОЛЬ ЖИЛИЩНОЙ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ В СИСТЕМЕ КОМПЛЕКСНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ МЕЗОУРОВНЯ.....	446
<i>Далиев Ахтам Шарафудинович</i>	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INSON RESURLARINI BOSHQARISHDA XORIJ TAJRIBALARINING ZARURLIGI.....	454
<i>Abdullayev Dostonbek G'ofurjon o'g'li</i>	
TURISTIK KLASTERLARNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA ULARNING HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI.....	458
<i>Xaitov Oxunjon Nomoz o'g'li</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA RESURS TA'MINOTI BOSHQARUVINING NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI VA MODELLARI.....	462
<i>Arziqulova Oybar chin Eshquvat qizi</i>	
XIZMATLAR SEKTORIDA RAQAMLI INNOVATSIYALAR VA MIJOZLAR EHTIYOJLARINI QONDIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	467
<i>Xudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich</i>	
СОЦИАЛЬНО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ СУЩНОСТЬ ПОДГОТОВКИ КАДРОВ В РАЗВИТИИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА.....	472
<i>Базаров Бердымурад Улугмуродович, Атавуллаева Саида Джумабекмуродовна</i>	
TURIZM SOHASIDA KADRLAR SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI.....	478
<i>Ho'jaqulov Bobur Rustam o'g'li</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DAVLATNING RO'LI	483
<i>Nabiyeva Muxabbat Djabirxanovna</i>	
"HOW GREEN INVESETMENTS CAN EFFECT ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES"	485
<i>Farangiz Ma'rufjonovna Pirmatova</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA UZOQ MUDDATLI RESURLAR MANBALARI VA ULARNING HAJMINI OSHIRISHNING ZARURIYATI.....	493
<i>Abduraxmonov Akmal Nurmat o'g'li</i>	
GLOBAL BOSHQARUV VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALARNING ROLI	498
<i>M.Sh. Tolipov</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВОЙ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ	504
<i>Буранбаева Шоира Рустамовна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA PIYOZ YETISHTIRISHDA TOMCHILATIB SUG'ORISHNI QO'LLASH ISTIQBOLLARI	508
<i>Suyunov Shohzodbek Murod o'g'li</i>	
YENGIL SANOAT KORXONALARINING RIVOJLANISHIGA BOSHQARUV MADANIYATIDAN FOYDALANISHNING TA'SIRI.....	513
<i>Aknazarova Zebiniso Bagdadovna</i>	
ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUVNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZM SAMARADORLIGINI ANIQLASH USULLARI	518
<i>Qurbaniyazov Shaxzodbek Karimovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA JOYLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY ASOSLARI	524
<i>Salimov Burxon Abubakirovich</i>	
"YASHIL" IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA UNDA ENERGIYADAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	530
<i>Berdiyeva Aziza G'anisher qizi</i>	

SIRKULAR IQTISODIYOTDAN KORXONA VA TADBIRKORLAR MANFAATLARI	535
Sodikov Zokir Rustamovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK SOHASIDA ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY BAZANI ISHLAB CHIQISH.....	541
Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Ubaydullayev Toxirjon Abdullajanovich	
MINTAQA OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARI CHAKANA SAVDOSIDA SHADOW WAREHOUSE MODELIGA ASOSLANGAN YETKAZIB BERISH TIZIMINI JORIY QILISH.....	548
Ibrayimova Dilnoza Abdisherpovna	
XIZMATLAR SAVDOSI SOHASIDA O'ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO HAMKORLIK IMKONIYATLARI	555
Qodirjonov A.M.	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RESURLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH KONSEPSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH USLUBIYOTI.....	559
Madraximova Gulasal Ro'zimboy qizi	
ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ СМАРТ-ТУРИЗМА И ИХ ПРИМЕНИМОСТЬ К КУЛЬТУРНОМУ НАСЛЕДИЮ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	564
Салихбаев Нурсултон Равшанович	
IJTIMOIIY NIHOYA TIZIMI VA IJTIMOIIY TIBBIY XIZMATLAR O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	572
Shanazarov Farrux Shodiyorovich	
ТЕХНИКО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ РАЗРАБОТКИ МОБИЛЬНОГО ПРИЛОЖЕНИЯ JOB VARAKA ДЛЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	577
Еримбетова Улбосын Маратовна	
TASHQI SAVDO VA INVESTITSIYALAR TAHLILI HAMDA ULARNING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	582
Jalolov Bekzod Sherzod o'g'li	
“O'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESLAR UCHUN SUN'IY INTELLEKT ASOSIDA MOLIYAVIY KO'RSATKICHLARNI TAHLIL QILISH VA RAQAMLI YECHIMLAR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH”	586
Azamatjon Mardayev Abdusamat o'g'li	
FARMATSEVIKA MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALARDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	591
Xudaynazarova Dilnoza Gafurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INNOVASION TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA KADRLAR TAYYORLASH MENEJMENTINING AMAL QILISH USULLARI VA TURLARI	596
Ergashev To'liqin Shokirovich	
HUDUDIIY IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH.....	602
Ibragimov Baxrom Baxodirovich	
ISLOMIY MOLIYA INSTRUMENTLARINI JORIY ETISH ORQALI O'ZBEKISTONDA MOLIYA BOZORINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI.....	606
Xodjayev Aziz Shovkatovich	
MAHALLIY HOKIMIYAT QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONLARIDA DINAMIK OMILLAR VA ULARNING INTEGRATSIYASI	611
Axmedov Farxod Raxmonjonovich	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL ETISH VA TAHLIL QILISH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	617
Rizakulov Abdurauf Abdimutalibovich	
ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ПРИВЛЕКАТЕЛЬНОСТИ ТУРИЗМА ЧЕРЕЗ КРЕАТИВНУЮ ИНДУСТРИЮ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН.....	623
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
IMITATION MODELDA AXBOROT NORAVSHANLIGI SABABLI YUZAGA KELADIGAN IQTISODIY SAMARASIZLIK TAHLILI.....	633
Qodirov Zohidjon Eralievich	

JISMONIY SHAXSLAR TOMONIDAN KREDITLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	637
Turdiyeva Kumush Erkinovna	
SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH XIZMATLARI SOHASIDA SIFATNI BAHOLASH KO'RSATKICHLARI VA IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIK O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK.....	641
Usmanova Nasiba Akbarjonovna, Eshbekova Xayriniso Baxtiyorovna	
SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR FAOLIYATINING SEGMENTATSIYASIGA ASOSLANIB SOLIQ XAVFLARINI ANIQLASH VA BAHOLASHNING AMALIY YONDOSHUVI	648
Elbaeva M.R.	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI.....	653
Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI SIFAT MENEJMENTI TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA TASHKIL ETISHNING XORIJ MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	657
Achilov Ilmurad	
MINTAQALAR INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING NAZARIY VA METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	663
Qobilov Anvar Eshpo'lotovich	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И ЦИФРОВЫХ ПОДХОДОВ В НАЛОГОВОМ ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬСТВЕ.....	669
Элбаева Мукаддас Рашидовна	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHDA KO'P MEZONLI TAHLIL USULLARINI QO'LLASH.....	674
Muxammadaliyev Mirzohidjon Muxammadali o'g'li	
BOJXONA HUDUDIDA QAYTA ISHLASH BOJXONA REJIMINING AMALDAGI HOLATI TAHLILI	681
Abdullayev Shaxzodbek	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH INTEGRATION OF RECREATION AND ECOTOURISM RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN	686
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	

ENSURING SUSTAINABLE REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT THROUGH INTEGRATION OF RECREATION AND ECOTOURISM RESOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN

Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna

TSUE, assistant professor of Tourism and hotel business department

Email: yusupovnanigor@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0006-4461-0144

Abstract. The article discusses the possibilities of combining recreational resources and ecotourism potential in Uzbekistan. The economic and social significance of the effective use of sanatorium-resort facilities, recreation areas and natural areas in the process of sustainable development is analyzed. The results of the study show that combining ecotourism with recreational opportunities contributes to the creation of new tourism products, diversification of regional tourism and maintenance of ecological balance.

Key words: ecotourism, recreational resources, sanatorium-resort facilities, regional tourism, sustainable development.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada O'zbekistonda rekreatsion resurslar va ekoturizm salohiyatini uyg'unlashtirish imkoniyatlari muhokama qilinadi. Barqaror rivojlanish jarayonida sanatoriy-kurort obyektlari, dam olish zonolari va tabiiy hududlardan samarali foydalanishning iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy ahamiyati tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, ekoturizmni rekreatsion imkoniyatlar bilan uyg'unlashtirish yangi turizm mahsulotlarini yaratish, mintaqaviy turizmni diversifikatsiya qilish va ekologik muvozanatni saqlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ekoturizm, rekreatsion resurslar, sanatoriy-kurort obyektlari, mintaqaviy turizm, barqaror rivojlanish.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются возможности сочетания рекреационных ресурсов и потенциала экотуризма в Узбекистане. Анализируется экономическое и социальное значение эффективного использования санаторно-курортных учреждений, зон отдыха и природных территорий в процессе устойчивого развития. Результаты исследования показывают, что объединение экотуризма с рекреационными возможностями способствует созданию новых туристических продуктов, диверсификации регионального туризма и поддержанию экологического баланса.

Ключевые слова: экотуризм, рекреационные ресурсы, санаторно-курортные учреждения, региональный туризм, устойчивое развитие.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the tourism sector in our country has been developing not only as an additional source of economic growth, but also as an important factor in the comprehensive development of regions, the creation of new jobs, and the improvement of the living standards of the population. This process plays a special role in ensuring the diversification of the national economy, expanding the share of the services sector, and strengthening the country's competitiveness on the international stage.

According to the World Tourism Organization (UN-Tourism), sustainable tourism involves the wise use of environmental resources, the conservation of natural processes, and the protection of biodiversity and natural heritage. At the same time, it ensures long-term economic stability and serves to create a sustainable source of income, jobs and social opportunities for local populations.

The report "Tourism and the Sustainable Development Goals - Journey to 2030", prepared in collaboration with UNWTO and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), notes that properly planned and effectively managed tourism not only helps to preserve natural and cultural heritage, but also strengthens local communities and expands trade and economic opportunities. Therefore, ecotourism is seen as a factor that enhances socio-economic stability in regions, along with ensuring ecological sustainability, preserving natural resources and protecting the interests of local residents. In this regard, the development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan is of great importance not only in preserving the natural landscape and rich biodiversity, but also in creating additional economic opportunities through their effective use. Recreational resources, including sanatoriums, resorts, health and prevention centers, play an important role in meaningfully organizing the population's free time, forming a healthy lifestyle and improving demographic health indicators. If these facilities are developed in harmony with ecotourism activities, they can serve to increase socio-economic efficiency in regions, alleviate the problem of seasonality of tourism, and expand the capabilities of local infrastructure.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In recent years, the economic importance of ecotourism and recreational tourism has been studied separately in international and domestic studies. According to UNWTO (2023), ecotourism has an average annual growth rate of 5–7% in the global tourism industry and accounts for a significant share of international tourism revenues. The main economic advantages are attracting foreign investment, creating new jobs, and investing in regional infrastructure. In Uzbekistan, the integration of ecotourism and recreational resources is also considered an important direction for increasing economic efficiency.

International experience shows that ecotourism clusters not only generate direct tourism revenues, but also have a multifaceted positive impact on the regional economy. For example, Liu (2022) highlighted the contribution of tourism to regional economic growth, including multiplier effects that stimulate transport, trade, services and agricultural sectors. Similarly, Kozhokulov et al. (2019) used the example of the Issyk-Kul region to demonstrate the role of ecotourism in the development of local production, employment and social services.

This experience is also relevant in the conditions of Uzbekistan, and through the development of agrotourism, ecosanatoriums and wellness ecotourism, it is possible to create sustainable sources of income in rural areas, improve the living standards of the local population and ensure economic diversification. The economic approach is also a priority in the research of local scientists. M. Jorayev (2019) indicates that recreational tourism reduces healthcare costs and increases labor productivity of the population as economic benefits. N. Karimova (2021) argues that the development of ecotourism allows attracting foreign investment, generating new tax revenues, and increasing local budget revenues. From this point of view, the integration of recreational and ecotourism resources:

- creates a market for additional services through new tourism products;
- increases foreign exchange earnings due to the influx of foreign tourists;
- provides jobs and sources of income for the local population;
- attracts investment in the modernization of regional infrastructure and transport networks;
- generates additional tax revenues for the state budget.

In general, the literature review shows that the integration of ecotourism and recreational tourism is considered an important factor in Uzbekistan not only diversifying the tourism sector, but also accelerating regional economic growth and ensuring international competitiveness.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study aims to analyze the process of integrating recreation and ecotourism resources in Uzbekistan from an economic and social perspective. Scientific and theoretical concepts of recreation and ecotourism, international experience, and research by local scientists were studied. Reports of the World Tourism Organization (UN-Tourism) and other international organizations were used as additional sources. Key indicators of the current state of recreation and ecotourism were summarized. The experience of Uzbekistan was compared with regional countries (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan) and international practice. Strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats in the integration of recreation and ecotourism resources were identified.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Recreational resources and their importance. Recreational resources are an important component of the tourism sector, which play a special role in the formation of a healthy lifestyle in society, the development of a recreational culture of the population, and the increase in the socio-economic potential of regions. These resources include sanatoriums and resorts, health and prevention centers, recreation centers, and sports and recreation facilities. Their activities are aimed not only at providing medical and preventive services, but also at meaningful spending of the population's free time.

In Uzbekistan, sanatoriums and health resorts form a wide network and operate in all regions of the country. These facilities provide services based on mineral springs, balneological resources, healing climatic conditions and natural landscapes. This allows them to ensure their competitiveness at the international level. In this regard, these institutions have great potential as tourism resources that serve not only to improve the health of the local population, but also to attract foreign tourists. In addition, sanatorium-resorts are also important by developing regional tourism infrastructure, creating additional jobs and providing an additional source of income to the local economy. Their effective operation, if carried out in integration with ecotourism areas, can become an important factor in sustainable development in the regions.

Uzbekistan has a wide range of natural and geographical conditions for the development of ecotourism. In particular, the country's mountainous regions, national parks, reserves, as well as water resources such as rivers and lakes, create great opportunities for organizing ecotourism activities. The rational use of these resources is an important factor not only in ensuring ecological sustainability, but also in increasing the economic interests of the local population and attracting foreign tourists.

For example, the Ugam-Chatkal National Park is of particular importance with its unique flora and fauna, mountainous landscapes and ecotourism trails. The Kitab National Reserve also offers extensive opportunities for the development of ecological tourism with its natural diversity, endemic fauna and flora. The Zarafshan Valley, with its mountain-forest landscapes, healing climate and ethnographic values, allows for the development of various forms of ecotourism. The Amu Darya Delta, the Aral Sea regions and desert ecosystems on the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are of particular interest for ecological and extreme tourism. In addition, the potential of ecotourism is not limited to natural resources, but can be further enriched by integrating it with the traditional lifestyle of the local population, national traditions and ethnographic heritage. In this regard, the development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan is an important means of achieving economic efficiency, as well as environmental sustainability and preserving cultural heritage.

The integration of recreational and ecotourism resources in the tourism sector is one of the most pressing issues today. Because the integration of these two areas serves not only to create new tourism products, but also to accelerate the economic, social and ecological development of regions. First of all, the possibility of forming new tourism products based on integration arises. For example, eco-sanatoriums, wellness ecotourism programs or "green resort" type resorts provide not only health services, but also provide an opportunity to maintain ecological balance and relax in harmony with nature. This meets the needs of modern tourists based on environmental responsibility. Secondly, the harmonious development of recreation and ecotourism resources will serve to accelerate regional economic development. Because this process will lead to the formation of new tourism infrastructure, the expansion of the service sector, and the emergence of regional tourism clusters. As a result, additional investments will be attracted and the competitiveness of the region will increase. Thirdly, one of the important aspects of integration is to increase employment of the local population and ensure environmental sustainability. The activities of recreational and ecotourism facilities not only create new jobs, but also have a positive impact on the lifestyle of the local population. At the same time, tourism activities based on ecological responsibility allow for the rational use of natural resources, their preservation for future generations, and adherence to the principles of sustainable development.

In general, the integration of recreation and ecotourism resources is considered one of the important mechanisms for increasing the competitiveness of the tourism industry, strengthening economic efficiency and ensuring environmental sustainability. It allows assessing existing practices in the tourism sector and identifying effective directions based on the experience of developed countries. Countries such as Germany, Switzerland and Turkey have achieved high economic efficiency through the successful integration of recreation and ecotourism. For example, Switzerland has combined sanatorium and resort services with mountain ecotourism, ensuring a stable flow of tourists throughout the year. Turkey, on the other hand, has increased its competitiveness in the international tourism market by integrating health and wellness tourism with sea resorts (Table 1).

Table 1. Aspects of the applicability of foreign best practices for Uzbekistan¹

States	Development direction	Strengths	Possible uses for Uzbekistan
Germany	Sanatorium-resort and wellness tourism	High quality of service, attention to environmental sustainability, international certification	Bringing services into line with international standards and strengthening environmental requirements
Switzerland	Mountain ecotourism and wellness	Excellent infrastructure, clean environment, stable tourist flow all year round	Integrating mountain areas with ecotourism, preserving a clean ecological environment
Turkey	Resort and wellness ecotourism	Wellness + marine tourism integration, strong marketing, investors attracted	Combining wellness and ecotourism, strengthening marketing campaigns

Compared with the experience of Uzbekistan, ecotourism infrastructure, service quality and marketing strategies are much more developed in these countries. At the same time, in the experience of Germany and Switzerland, environmental sustainability and resource protection are formed as the main priority areas. In Uzbekistan, however, the differences can be reduced by modernizing the material and technical base of recreational facilities, establishing services in accordance with international standards, and widely using digital marketing tools. Therefore, benchmarking analysis serves as an important method for Uzbekistan to diversify tourism by adapting foreign best practices to local conditions.

Cluster analysis allows you to identify regional specialization by grouping tourism resources according to territorial characteristics. The natural and geographical conditions, recreational facilities and ecotourism resources available in Uzbekistan create ample opportunities for the formation of various clusters. For example, mountain ecotourism and sports tourism clusters can be developed in the Hissar mountains and Zamin mountains. Karakalpakstan and the Kyzylkum deserts constitute a separate direction for desert ecotourism and ecological expeditions. In historical cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand and Khiva, recreational tourism combines with cultural heritage sites and forms integrated clusters with health centers (Table 2).

Table 2. Cluster-based development of recreational and ecotourism resources in Uzbekistan²

Region	Tourism sector (cluster)	Opportunities
Zaamin, Hissar Mountains	Mountain ecotourism, sports and extreme tourism	Trekking, skiing, mountain sports, ecological routes
Karakalpakstan, Kyzylkum	Desert ecotourism, ecological expeditions	Sahara safari, archaeological tourism, ecological observation
Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva	Recreational + cultural tourism cluster	Sanatoriums, cultural heritage sites, wellness integration
Fergana Valley, Kashkadarya region	Agro- and ethno-ecotourism cluster	Agricultural tourism, national crafts, local culture
Surkhandarya, Zarafshan valley	Ecotourism in nature reserves and national parks	Surkhan Reserve, Zarafshan mountains, unique flora and fauna
Tashkent region (Chatqol, Ugam)	National park and mountain tourism	Ugam-Chatkal National Park, mountain tourism, ecological recreation

The clustering process helps to ensure the integrated use of tourism resources, increase economic efficiency and ensure interregional competitiveness. In addition, the cluster-based planning of infrastructure projects, employment of the local population and attraction of foreign investments expands. Therefore, the development of recreational and ecotourism resources in Uzbekistan on the basis of clusters is an important factor not only in the effective implementation of regional tourism policy, but also in the formation of a national tourism brand.

Today, the issue of developing ecotourism in Uzbekistan is supported at the level of state policy. Tourism development strategies and regulatory legal acts adopted in recent years are aimed at preserving the country's natural and cultural heritage and their effective use through the tourism sector. However, despite the existing

¹ Benchmarking analysis. Author's development

² Author's development

opportunities, there are a number of factors that hinder the full development of ecotourism. First of all, the lack of infrastructure is a serious obstacle to the full realization of the potential of ecotourism. Mountainous regions and reserves are often insufficiently developed in terms of transport and communications, which reduces the flow of tourists. Secondly, the lack of foreign investment makes it difficult to implement ecotourism projects on a large scale. Initiatives implemented by local business entities in many cases remain insufficiently effective due to limited financial resources. Thirdly, restrictions in the training of specialists lead to a shortage of qualified personnel in the ecotourism sector. This affects the quality of service and the organization of tourism activities in line with international requirements.

Therefore, it is important to effectively use the potential of recreational facilities in the country, to form new ecotourism routes and promote them in the international market. In addition, the widespread involvement of local residents in tourism activities, improving their service culture and supporting small businesses are among the necessary conditions for the sustainable development of ecotourism. The rational use of recreational and ecotourism resources through an integrated approach will ensure the ecological and economic stability of the country.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In Uzbekistan, the integration of recreational and ecotourism resources will ensure the diversification of the tourism sector, support sustainable development, and increase the country's competitiveness in the international tourism market. This process will not only increase economic efficiency, but also serve to protect the environment, preserve cultural heritage, and protect the interests of local residents.

One of the most important tasks in this direction is the development of eco-infrastructure. Improving transport, communication, and service systems in mountainous areas, reserves, and national parks will create the basis for the rapid development of ecotourism. At the same time, expanding international cooperation will allow attracting foreign investment, adopting best practices, and bringing the quality of tourism services into line with international standards. Another important issue is to strengthen scientific research, since scientifically based decisions are necessary for the rational use of tourism resources, ensuring environmental sustainability, and introducing innovative approaches.

In general, the combination of recreational and ecotourism resources will take Uzbekistan's tourism sector to a new level and make the country internationally recognized as an environmentally responsible and attractive tourist destination.

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